

Turning Waste into a Solution: Drinking Water Treatment Residuals as a Low-Cost Adsorbent for Antibiotic Removal

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Abstract

The presence of emerging contaminants, especially antibiotics, has raised global concern. One of the main sources of antibiotics into the environment is wastewater, which is why efforts have been made to introduce new treatment methods for the antibiotic's removal. The use of drinking water treatment residuals (DWTR) as a low-cost adsorbent may become a sustainable option for removing antibiotics. The objective of this study was to analyse and explore the potential of DWTR as an adsorbent of sulfamethoxazole (SMX) and trimethoprim (TMP) in continuous flow conditions using a fixed-bed column. The breakthrough curves reveal differences between the antibiotic's adsorption onto DWTR, which may be related to the compounds' electrostatic interactions and hydrophobic properties. DWTR showed better performance for TMP, with a removal efficiency of 51%, compared to 35% for SMX. This preliminary study highlights the potential of DWTR as a low-cost adsorbent for antibiotics, with adsorption capacities comparable to other low-cost options, without requiring any kind of activation or additional treatment.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

Sustainable adsorbents; antibiotics; drinking water treatment residuals; circular economy;

INTRODUCTION

Emerging contaminants in wastewater, especially antibiotics, are raising concerns about antimicrobial resistance (AMR). According to the World Health Organization, AMR is a threat not only to public health but also to food security and the economy (Vasilachi et al., 2021). To prevent AMR, it is crucial to prevent the release of antibiotics into the environment (Sambaza & Naicker, 2023) since Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTP) are one of the main sources of antibiotics into the environment, which makes WWTP a hotspot for AMR (Imwene et al., 2022). AMR causes around 700,000 deaths annually, and by 2050 this number may reach 10 million deaths. This highlights the importance of reducing the presence of antibiotics in the environment to safeguard public health (Sambaza & Naicker, 2023). Sulfamethoxazole (SMX) and Trimethoprim (TMP) are two commonly detected antibiotics in the effluents of WWTPs due to their high resistance to the conventional wastewater treatments (Kovalakova et al., 2020). The widespread presence of these antibiotics and their environmental and public health impacts highlight the need to adapt wastewater treatment to effectively remove or eliminate them with additional treatments. (Chaves et al., 2022). Among the complementary treatments for the removal of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs), such as antibiotics, the adsorption process stands out as the most promising option, namely due to its low operational and energy costs compared with other methods, such as advanced oxidation processes or membrane technologies (Dias et al., 2021). Within the scope of adsorption processes, the current focus is the study of low-cost adsorbents (Li et al., 2019; Mitra et al., 2021). Drinking water treatment residuals (DWTR) have been tested as a suitable adsorbent material for CECs such as hormones, antibiotics and anti-depressive drugs (Dias et al., 2021; Kulandaivelu et al., 2020; Sousa et al., 2024). However, the majority of the reported studies were conducted in batch conditions, highlighting a gap in understanding the performance of DWTR in a fixed-bed column, operating in continuous mode. This study aimed to further explore the potential of DWTR as an adsorbent in continuous flow conditions, thereby demonstrating this sustainable resource's promising potential in waste

management, wastewater treatment and circular economy within the water sector.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Drinking water treatment sludge

The DWTR sample was obtained from the drinking water treatment plant after the final dewatering stage. This material contained the chemicals used in the drinking water treatment process, specifically polyaluminum chloride, lime milk, activated carbon, and polyelectrolyte. The collected sludge was subjected to drying at 105 °C to eliminate any remaining moisture (Sousa et al., 2025). The sludge samples were dried in air and subsequently at a constant temperature of 105°C to remove any residual moisture. Table 1 presents the DWTR characterisation results.

Table 1. DWTR characteristics (Adapted from Sousa et al. (2024))

	Value
Ash content (w/w%)	58.40
Carbon content (w/w%)	21.67
Hydrogen content (w/w%)	2.55
Nitrogen content (w/w%)	0.74
Sulphur content (w/w%)	0.00
Oxygen content (w/w%)	16.60
pH at the point of zero charge (pH _{PZC})	5.50
Surface area (m ² /g)	165.00
Total pore volume (cm ³ /g)	0.15

Fixed bed column adsorption experiment

The continuous adsorption experiment was conducted in a glass column with 0.5 cm of internal diameter connected to a peristaltic pump positioned at the base of the column to ensure ascending flow. The fixed bed experiments were performed with 0.5 g of DWTR (2.5 cm of bed height) and a flow of 0.001 L/min (optimized conditions).. The adsorbate monocomponent solutions were prepared using distilled water with 1 % methanol (MeOH) and the antibiotic (TMP or SMX) at neutral pH conditions (pH = 7.0). The SMX and TMP initial concentration (C₀) was 20 ppm. The samples were collected from the column outlet at different time intervals to obtain the breakthrough curves. The quantification of the two antibiotics was performed using UV-Vis spectroscopy. The column performance, for each antibiotic, was assessed by defining the breakthrough time (t_r, min) as the moment when the outlet concentration reached 5% of C₀ and the saturation time (t_s, min) when the outlet concentration achieved 90% of C₀. The total mass of adsorbate in the column until the saturation point (m_{adsorbate}, mg), the total mass of adsorbate adsorbed by the adsorbent at the saturation point (m_{total}, mg), the total adsorption capacity of the column (q_{total}, mg/g), and column removal efficiency (RE, %) were determined using to the Eq. (1), Eq. (2), Eq. (3), and Eq. (4):

$$m_{\text{adsorbate}} = \frac{Q \cdot C_0 \cdot t_s}{1000} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

$$m_{\text{total}} = \frac{Q \cdot C_0}{1000} \int_0^{t_s} \left(1 - \frac{C_t}{C_0}\right) dt \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

$$q_{total} = \frac{m_{total}}{m_{adsorbent}} \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

$$RE = \left(\frac{m_{total}}{m_{adsorbate}} \right) \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

Where Q (L/min) is the flow, C_{t_s} (mg/L) is the concentration at the saturation point and $m_{adsorbent}$ (g) is the mass of DWTR.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The breakthrough curves (Figure 1) revealed differences in the adsorption behaviour of antibiotics. One significant difference was that the t_r for SMX was 2 minutes, while for TMP, the t_r was achieved only at 87 minutes. The electrostatic repulsion between SMX and DWTR may explain this behaviour. At neutral pH, SMX is deprotonated ($pK_{a2} = 5.7$) (Esteki et al., 2020), while DWTR carries a negative charge (Table 1). However, the saturation for TMP was achieved earlier ($t_s = 524$ minutes) than for SMX ($t_s = 1577$ minutes). This may be due to the hydrophobic properties of the molecules. TMP has an octanol-water partition coefficient (Log Kow) ranging from 2.2 to 2.6, whereas SMX has a Log Kow range of 0.8 to 1.8. Consequently, TMP has a greater tendency to be adsorbed compared to SMX, leading to faster adsorption kinetics of TMP, as reported by Xue et al. (2023). The hydrophobic properties and the electrostatic interactions also reflect on the RE achieved; for TMP, the RE was 51%, while for SMX, the RE was significantly lower at 35%. The uptake capacities DWTR adsorption capacity for SMX (21.1 mg/g) was higher than for TMP (15.3 mg/g), these values are comparable with other low-cost adsorption in fixed bed column tests. (Ahmed, 2017; Juela et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Breakthrough curves: a) trimethoprim and b) sulfamethoxazole

CONCLUSION

This study showed preliminary results of the adsorption of SMX and TMP onto DWTR in continuous adsorption conditions. Based on the breakthrough curves, it was possible to conclude that the adsorption was influenced by electrostatic interactions and hydrophobicity properties of the compounds. DWTR performance was better for TMP, with a removal efficiency of 51%, while for SMX, the efficiency achieved was 35%. This study highlights DWTR as a promising low-cost adsorbent for antibiotics, with adsorption capacities comparable to other low-cost options without requiring activation, reinforcing the idea of a promising sustainable adsorbent and contributing to the circular economy within the water sector. Future research should aim to optimize continuous flow

conditions to establish the dimensional parameters necessary for full-scale pilots.

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